

Impact of Soil Management on Carbon Sequestration and Erodibility Status in Yorro Local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria

Mansur Abdul Mohammed^a, Ibrahim Danjuma Andesiye^b, Sule Haruna Bibot^c

^{a&b}Department of Geography, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria.

^cDepartment of Social Studies and Environmental Education, Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Email: mamohammed.geog@buk.edu.ng

PAPER KEYWORDS ABSTRACT

Carbon stock, Climate mitigation, Erosion, Soil, Vulnerability.

Fluctuation of precipitation and temperature due to climatic inconsistency, coupled with soil management practices, upsets the soil ecosystem by degrading its quality, and consequently, its carbon sequestration capacity declines. The study assessed the effects of soil management on carbon sequestration for sustainable management and climate change mitigation. Three soil managements: plantation, cultivated, and grazing were purposively selected, whereby 10 soil samples were collected and analysed for particle size distribution, organic matter, bulk density, mean weight diameter, and very fine sand using standard laboratory procedures, and soil carbon stock was evaluated. The result shows significant variation in the concentration of soil carbon stock among the management. Plantation has the highest carbon stock (2.036%) and infiltration rate (2.280%) among other management practices. Cultivated management has a higher erodibility of 0.0455 Mg h/MJ/mm, grazing (0.0452 Mg h/MJ/mm) and plantation (0.0258 Mg h/MJ/mm), indicating that cultivated management is highly vulnerable to erosion and carbon emission, consequently leading to climate variability. It was concluded that soil management practices significantly influence soil quality and its ability to mitigate climate change by sequestering soil carbon. Reduction in over-cultivation and grazing is encouraged by practising fallow management and providing more grazing to reduce the negative impact of over-cultivation and grazing on the carbon sequestration in the area.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19852604>

1.1. Introduction

Land is a valuable natural resource utilised for the cultivation of crops, settlements of population, creation of dams and reservoirs, development of industries and maintaining forests and Wildlife. Any kind of permanent or cyclic intervention of land is called land use. It is the surface utilisation of a vacant or developed land for a clear purpose, at a given time. The economic value or potential of a region or area depends upon the land use properties. Land use is an emerging socioeconomic activity wherein a region or place is used for one major specific purpose (Balasubramanian, 2016).

Soil erosion is known as an important economic, environmental and social disaster (Taleshian Ghajar and Emadi, 2018). Soil erosion is described as the detachment and removal of surface particles from soil as a result of wind or rainfall. Soil loss is a worldwide concern which threatens soil and water resources. Soil, as the most important component of an ecosystem, can secure food production, enhance the water resources and promote the biodiversity and carbon sequestration if it is well managed (Taleshian et al., 2018). The main parameter in soil erosion is the inherent soil characteristics, which is called the soil erodibility factor. Type and rate of soil erosion/loss in an area depend on different factors, including climate, geomorphology, soil type and land use. Considering the different factors involved in soil loss, land use is the most important one due to the potentially destructive role of human effects. Land use change and agricultural development cause large changes to soil characteristics, which make soils susceptible to erosion and degradation. Land use change has an adverse effect on soil characteristics such as permeability, soil texture and aggregate stability. Changes in these characteristics are important because they lead to changes in the rate of soil erodibility (Taleshian et al., 2018).

Land use is considered the arrangements, activities and inputs people undertake in a certain land cover type to produce, change or maintain it (Ufot, 2016). Successful agriculture requires the sustainable use of soil resources, because soil can easily lose its quality and quantity within a short period of time for different reasons such as intensive cultivation, leaching and soil erosion (Kiflu and Beyene, 2013). Land use change is a complex process shaped by human activity and affected by ecological, economic and social drivers capable of influencing a wide range of environmental and economic conditions. Soil is one of the most abundant natural resources that sustains biological life. It plays a crucial role in agricultural production. A variety of farming practices often lead to some forms of soil degradation, such as soil erosion (Yusuf, Oguntunde and Lawal, 2018). Soil erosion impacts negatively on crop productivity and environmental quality and depresses the socioeconomic status of farmers; it is therefore a threat to the landowners' livelihoods as well as the overall health of an ecosystem.

Erodibility is the susceptibility of a soil to erosion. Abata et al. (2016) described erodibility as the inherent tendency of soils to erode at different rates due solely to differences in soil properties. The soil erodibility factor is an estimate of the ability of soils to resist erosion based on the physical characteristics of each soil. It is a quantitative description of the susceptibility of soil particles to detachment and transport by rainfall and runoff. Erodibility factor is the rate of erosion per unit erosion index from a standard plot. The factors that influence soil erodibility are soil characteristics such as permeability, infiltration, water holding capacity, distribution of particles, aggregate stability, tendency towards dispersion and abrasion, transportability, structure and humus content (Abata et al., 2016).

In recent years, Olubanjo (2016) have used the USLE-K factor as an indicator of soil erosion, because it is a measure of soil susceptibility to erosion, where he said soil under native grass and conventional tillage would behave differently in terms of aggregate size distribution, aggregate stability and erosion. The study aims to assess the effects of some land use management on soil erodibility and the socio-economic impact of soil erosion in Yorro Local Government Area of Taraba State.

1.2. Research Methods

Yorro Local Government Area was created in 1991. It lies between latitude 8° 42'N to 9° 12'N and longitude 1° 20'E to 11° 45' E, with a land area of about 1,304 km² (Oruonye, 2013). The LGA is bounded to the north by Lau LGA, to the northeast and southeast by Mayo Belwa (Adamawa State), to the east by Zing LGA, to the west by Jalingo LGA and to the south by Bali LGA (Oruonye, 2013). It has a humid tropical climate characterised by alternating periods of dry and wet spells determined by the movement of the Intertropical Convergence Zone as well as the effect of relief (Salzmann *et al.*, 2002). Yorro LGA is underlain predominantly by the Precambrian granite rock of the basement complex, and the soil types are predominantly ferruginous tropical soils and lithosols of Nigeria, based on the genetic soil classification (Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), 2007). The study area falls within the northern guinea savannah belt of Nigeria, and the vegetation is made up of grasses, aquatic and dry land weeds, interspersed with shrubs and Trees (Bakoji, 2017). Major land use management is residential, soil mining, and agricultural (grazing, plantation, cultivation).

Data Collection

Three land uses (grazing, cultivated, and plantation) were purposively selected because they cover the major land use management influencing soil erosion in the area. In each land use identified, 100 small squares (grids) of 100m² were superimposed on it, and 10 grids were systematically selected for soil sampling using equation 1.

$$\text{Sampling interval (SI)} \frac{100}{10} = 10 \quad 1$$

In each grid identified, a point composite sampling method was adopted whereby five samples were collected in each grid, mixed appropriately and homogeneously to form a bulk sample within which 0.5kg was collected (composite sample). The samples collected were labelled appropriately and then taken to the laboratory for the analysis of bulk density, particle size distribution, organic matter and mean weight diameter. Proper care was taken to avoid sample contamination.

In each selected sample grid, point composite sampling techniques were used to collect half a kg of soil at a depth of 15cm (upper stratum of the soil) using a soil auger. This is a depth with the greatest agricultural significance as it covers the root zones of most crops, and it constitutes the upper stratum of the soil where surface erosion begins. The collected samples from each sampled point in a given land use were transferred into a polyethene bag labelled appropriately and then taken to the laboratory for further analysis of some soil properties that are related to soil erosion.

Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the data analysis. The descriptive statistics used include: mean and percentage, whereas the inferential statistics used are: standard deviation and analysis of variance. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the variability of the USLE K-factor among the three land uses. The nature and strength of the relationship between k-factors and some physicochemical properties influencing soil erosion were evaluated using Pearson correlation. All the

analyses were carried out using Excel (2013) and the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.

Estimation of the USLE K-Factor

The soil erodibility (K factor) is generally estimated using updated equations in which K, the soil erodibility factor, reflects the susceptibility of a soil type to erosion, which was calculated using equation 2 (Wischmeier, 1978, and Wischmeier and Smith, 1979).

$$K = 2.8M^{1.14} \times 10^{-7} \times (12 - \%OM) + 4.3 \times 10^{-3} (S-2) + 3.3 \times 10^{-3}(P-3) \quad 2$$

Where K is the erodibility of soil (Mg h/MJ/mm), M is the product of (100 – clay %) × (very fine sand (0.05 – 0.1mm) + % silt), and OM refers to organic matter (%). The P coefficient was obtained through the measurement of infiltration rate by the double rings method, and the S coefficient was determined using the shape and the size of soil aggregates (Vaezi *et al.*, 2008).

1.3. Results and Discussion

Table 1 indicates that bulk density is highest in grazing land use (1.352g/cm³), followed by cultivated land use (1.199g/cm³) and the least is observed in plantation land use soil (1.145g/cm³). High value for bulk density in grazing land use is due to the constant trampling of the land by livestock, exerting their weight upon the land, thereby compacting the soil. Also, cultivation of the soil for cropping, particularly using heavy machines like tractors, compacts the soil, resulting in high bulk density. This soil compaction impedes infiltration of water into the soil and makes the soil more resistant to detachment by agents of denudation. This is in line with the study by Olubanjo (2016) that indicates the least bulk density in plantation land use.

Table 1. Physicochemical Properties of Soil Related to Soil Erosion

Land Uses	Stat.	D _b (g/cm ³)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	OM (%)	MWD (mm)	Infltrn (cm/h)	VFS (%)
Plantation	\bar{x}	1.145	78.65	10.3	11.148	2.036	0.63	2.28	18.56
	$\pm SD$	0.042	1.766	2.058	1.716	0.692	0.116	0.379	1.858
	CV	0.002	3.120	4.233	2.945	0.478	0.013	0.144	3.452
Cultivated	\bar{x}	1.199	81.14	12.0	6.86	1.509	0.55	1.62	31.932
	$\pm SD$	0.029	1.729	1.764	1.101	0.488	0.053	0.405	2.665
	CV	0.001	2.989	3.111	1.211	0.238	0.003	0.164	7.103
Grazing	\bar{x}	1.352	76.16	14.3	9.54	1.483	0.43	1.08	30.629
	$\pm SD$	0.059	2.530	2.111	0.738	0.292	0.048	0.473	2.188
	CV	0.003	6.4	4.456	0.544	0.085	0.002	0.224	4.787

D_b=bulk density, *OM*=Organic matter, *MWD*=mean weight diameter & *VFS*=very fine sand

Particle Size Distribution (PSD)

The result from Table 1 shows that the percentage values for PSD (sand, silt, and clay) vary across the land uses. Soil in cultivated land use has the highest amount of sand

content (81.14%), followed by soil in plantation land use (78.65%), and grazing land use has the least sand content (76.16%). Silt percentage is highest in grazing land use (14.3%), followed by soil in cultivated land use (12.0%), and the lowest silt content is in plantation land use (10.3%). The relatively higher percentage of silt content in grazing and cultivated land use, respectively, is a result of livestock trampling on the grazing land, which breaks the soil particles into smaller sizes. Also, soil tillage and land clearing for crop cultivation adversely break soil particles. This breaking and compaction of soil reduces infiltration and speeds up surface runoff, which consequently increases soil erosion vulnerability (Meseret, Addis, and Eyayu, 2016).

Furthermore, clay content is highest in soil of plantation land use (11.148%), next by soil in grazing land use (9.54%), and the least in clay content is soil in cultivated land use (6.86%). A high percentage of clay in plantation land was a result of fallen leaves and other plant biomass, which decomposed to form organic matter. This was reported by Brady and Well (2014), organic matter of the soil enhances the clay content of the soil and makes the soil less vulnerable to soil erosion. This is in line with the study by Meseret, Addis, and Eyayu (2016) that showed high clay content in Plantation land use.

Soil Organic Matter

From Table 1, the percentage of organic matter is highest in plantation land use (2.036%), followed by cultivated and grazing land uses, having organic matter content of 1.509% and 1.483%, respectively. The highest percentage of organic matter in plantation land use is due to plant litter (plant roots, leaves, etc.) that decomposes to humus in the soil. This is very important in the functioning of the soil system, as it increases soil porosity, thereby increasing infiltration and water-holding capacity of soil, providing more water availability for plants, hence making the soil less vulnerable to soil erosion. Vegetation is undoubtedly an important factor controlling the rain drop impact intensity and the frequency of overland flow, and consequently reduces soil erosion. Low organic matter content in cultivated and grazing land use is due to relatively low vegetation cover and crop uptake (Lawrence *et al.*, 2019).

Extensive cultivation of cereal crops like maize and millet is mainly carried out on ridges prepared by the removal of perennial vegetation. These areas become vulnerable to soil erosion because of the decreased protection by vegetation cover, which reduces effective rainfall intensity at the ground surface. Grazing on land reduces ground cover and enhances soil compaction, this result to low infiltration and excessive surface runoff by water during intensive rain fall. Erosion changes soil physical properties, mainly because of the removal (soil profile truncation) of surface soil rich in organic matter and exposure of lower soil layers. This is supported by Jankauskas and Fullen (2007), who reported that soils with low organic matter contents are more erodible than those with less organic matter, and generally soils with <2% organic matter content by weight are highly erodible. This is similar to the study by Lawrence *et al.* (2019), who presented the highest organic matter content on plantation land use.

Infiltration Rate

The results presented in Table 1 and Fig 4 indicate that the infiltration rate is highest in plantation land use (2.28cm/h), followed by cultivated land use (1.62cm/h) and the least was obtained in grazing land use (1.08cm/h). The highest infiltration rate in

plantation land use is attributed to higher vegetation cover and organic matter content, which reduces surface runoff, increases soil porosity and water holding capacity of soil, thereby decreasing soil vulnerability to erosion. Lower infiltration rates in cultivated and grazing land uses were due to the effect of cultivation and grazing of cattle, which reduces vegetation cover and increases soil compaction, resulting in excessive surface runoff and erosion vulnerability in the two land uses. However, this effect is more severe in grazing land use because of animal trampling, which leads to soil compaction. This is in agreement with the study by Olubanjo (2016) that indicated the highest infiltration rate in plantation land use.

Very Fine Sand (VFS)

Very fine sand (VFS) percentage is highest in cultivated and grazing land uses, with a value of 31.932% and 30.629%, respectively and lowest in plantation land use. The high percentage of very fine sand in cultivated and grazing land uses is due to the crushing of soil particles by heavy machines and implements used for ploughing and harrowing of soil during crop cultivation. Similarly, the hoofs of livestock crush soil particles into smaller sizes, thereby increasing the quantity of very fine sand in the soil (Yusuf *et al.*, 2018). These very fine sands are vulnerable to detachment and transportation by agents of denudation, hence increasing the land's vulnerability to soil erosion.

Mean Weight Diameter (MWD)

Mean weight diameter of soil aggregates describes soil aggregate stability or its resistance to breakdown under disruptive forces. The higher the value for MWD, the more stable the soil, and it is known to be tightly linked to soil erodibility (Barthes and Roose, 2002). Higher MWD (0.63mm) was obtained in vegetated land use, while 0.55mm and 0.43mm were obtained in cultivated and grazing land uses, respectively. Higher MWD in plantation land use is a result of relatively more stable soil particles free of human and other artificial interference that breaks or crushes the soil particles. This is supported by Yusuf *et al.* (2018), who reported high aggregate stability in plantation land use of the gully bed ecosystem.

Erodibility (K-Factor) Status of the Land Uses

The K-factor status usually expresses the vulnerability of soil to erosion, and this varies among the land uses due to inherent variation in the soil physicochemical properties as induced by the land use activities. To obtain the k-factor, there are predictive soil properties (parameters) needed for the computation. These parameters are percentage organic matter, clay, VFS and silt content. Also, soil permeability and structural codes are required for the calculation (the structural and permeability codes for both land uses are 2 and 3, respectively). Using equation 2, the K-factor for the three land uses is presented in Table 2.

Results presented in Table 2 show that the highest USLE K-factor (0.0455 Mg h/MJ/mm) was found in cultivated land use, followed by grazing land use (0.0452 Mg h/MJ/mm), while the lowest K-factor was obtained in plantation land use (0.0258 Mg h/MJ/mm). This is in accord with the study by Yusuf *et al.* (2018) on land use effects on soil erodibility and hydraulic conductivity in Akure, Nigeria, which reported a high value for the K-factor in grazed and cultivated land uses.

Table 2. Soil Erodibility (K-factor) Status of Plantation, Cultivated and Grazing Land Uses

Sample ID	Plantation land use (Mg h/MJ/mm)	Cultivated land use (Mg h/MJ/mm)	Grazing land use (Mg h/MJ/mm)
1	0.028177	0.045470	0.046209
2	0.028391	0.041293	0.046568
3	0.019211	0.040933	0.043785
4	0.025467	0.047340	0.047018
5	0.025498	0.050542	0.040450
6	0.026455	0.050846	0.051842
7	0.026119	0.043136	0.043620
8	0.023345	0.049138	0.040631
9	0.028854	0.046530	0.045529
10	0.026836	0.039515	0.046663
Mean (\bar{x})	0.0258	0.0455	0.0452

The mean K-factor value from the three land uses falls within the vulnerable range (0.02 – 0.69) as reported by Goldman, Jackson, and Bursztynsky (1986). The higher K-factor value in cultivated and grazing land uses is largely due to the intensive cultivation and grazing activities, which expose the soil to various forms of erosion. Cultivation activities like tillage practice fracture the soil, disrupt soil structure and reduce vegetation cover, hence making the soil vulnerable to soil erosion. Grazing activities, especially by cattle, deprive the soil of its protective vegetation cover. The constant trampling on the soil by livestock accelerates soil compaction, leading to low infiltration and excessive surface runoff, thereby making the soil more vulnerable to erosion.

Variation of K-factor Among Land Uses

Results obtained from Analysis of Variance (Table 2) indicate a significant variation in K-factor among the three land uses at alpha (0.05), as presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Variation of k-factor Among Land Uses Using ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.003	2	0.001	105.485	0.000
Within Group	0.000	27	0.000		
Total	0.003	29			

The k-factors among the land uses were further subjected to a post hoc test to determine where the difference actually emanated from, and the obtained results were presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Post Hoc test of k-factors among land uses

Land uses	Land uses	Mean diff.	Sig. value
Plantation land use	Cultivated land use	-0.0196390	0.000*
	Grazing land use	-0.0193962	0.000*
Cultivated land use	Plantation land use	0.0196390	0.000*
	Grazing land use	0.0002428	0.987

Grazing land use	Plantation land use	0.0193962	0.000*
	Cultivated land use	-0.0002428	0.987

* Significant at 0.05

The multiple comparison test using Tukey HSD (Table 4) revealed that there is a statistically significant difference between k-factor in plantation land use and cultivated land use, and also between k-factor in plantation land use and grazing land use. However, there is no statistically significant difference between k-factors in cultivated and grazing land uses.

Relationship Between Individual Predictive Parameter and K-factor

The Pearson product-moment correlation analysis (Table 5) revealed the relationship between k-factor and the predictive parameters (clay, organic matter, silt and VFS) in soils of the three land uses. The analysis shows the direction and strength of the relationship between the k-factor and the individual parameters.

Table 5. Relationship Between Individual Predictive Parameter and K-factor

Parameters (%)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	P-value
Plantation:		
Clay	-0.486	0.0003*
Organic matter	-0.641	0.0000*
Silt	0.482	0.0029*
VFS	0.348	0.1307
Cultivated:		
Clay	-0.088	0.0008*
Organic matter	-0.378	0.0000*
Silt	0.442	0.0060*
VFS	0.768	0.5103
Grazing:		
Clay	-0.146	0.0331*
Organic matter	-0.101	0.0001*
Silt	0.765	0.0007*
VFS	0.621	0.2483

* Significant at 0.05

The correlation between k-factor and clay content in soils of the land uses (Table 5) shows that k-factor has a weak negative correlation in plantation land use ($r = -0.486$), cultivated land use ($r = -0.088$) and in grazing ($r = -0.146$). However, there was a significant relationship between k-factor and clay content in soils of the land uses. This tallies with the study by Liu M. *et al.* (2020) that revealed a significant relationship between the percentage of clay in soil and k-factor in granite and limestone regions of China. It implies that an increase in the percentage of clay content of soils in the three land uses would decrease the k-factor accordingly because clay content increases, binds the soil particles together, and also increases the water-holding capacity of the soil.

The correlation of k-factor and the predictive parameters (physicochemical properties of the soil) as presented in Table 5 revealed that k-factor was negatively correlated with organic matter in soils of the land uses ($r = -0.641$ for plantation land use, $r = -0.378$ for

cultivated land use and $r = -0.101$ for grazing land use). A moderate negative relationship was observed in plantation land use, while a weak negative relationship was observed in cultivated and grazing land uses. However, there was a significant relationship between the k-factor and soil organic matter content in soils of the land uses. This agrees with the study by Giovannini *et al.* (2001) and Liu *et al.* (2020), which observed a significant relationship between the organic matter content of a soil and the k-factor. This indicates that an increase in organic matter content of the soils in the land uses would yield a corresponding decrease in k-factor value proportionately.

Correlation of k-factor and percentage of silt content in soils of the land uses (Table 7) reveals a significant positive correlation in plantation land ($r = 0.482$), cultivated land ($r = 0.442$) and grazing land ($r = 0.765$). A strong relationship was detected in grazing land use, while a moderate relationship was observed in plantation and cultivated land uses. This is in line with a study by Zhao *et al.* (2018) that revealed a significant correlation between k-factor and percentage silt content in soils of the Loess Plateau in China. It implies that an increase in percentage silt content in soils of the land uses would inform a directly proportional increase in the k-factor of soil.

The correlation of k-factor and VFS in soils of the land uses (Table 5) revealed a positive correlation in plantation ($r = 0.348$), cultivated ($r = 0.768$) and grazing ($r = 0.621$) land uses.

A strong relationship was observed in cultivated land use; a moderate relationship was observed in grazing land use, while a weak relationship existed in plantation land use. However, the correlation in all the land uses was significant at the chosen significant level (0.05). This is in accord with a study by Zhao W. *et al.* (2018) that revealed a significant correlation between k-factor and percentage of VFS in soils of the Loess plateau in China. This shows that the value for k-factor in soils of the land uses increases with a corresponding increase in the percentage of silt content.

1.4. Conclusion

After in-depth consideration of result of the research findings, it is logical enough to conclude that change and transformation of land in its natural state to cultivated and grazing lands degrades the natural soil structure, soil fertility, soil productivity, and negatively altered soil physicochemical properties which in turn accelerate soil erosion by making the soil very vulnerable to agents of erosion as affirmed by the USLE K-factor estimation, that shows soils in cultivated and grazing land uses have a significantly higher vulnerability levels to soil erosion compare to soil in plantation land use.

1.5. Recommendations

It is pertinent to take adequate care of the soil and protect it by managing the problem of soil erosion in Yorro LGA through the following measures:

1. Rotational grazing and the avoidance of over-grazing should be adopted to help reduce the intensity of the effects of grazing on the soil, such as compaction and clearing of vegetation that provides cover to the soil.
2. Environmental impacts of soil mining land use in Yorro LGA, Taraba State. This will reveal the devastating effects of soil mining with a possible way forward for the betterment of the environment.

1.6. References

- Abata, S., Tiza, M., Iorwua, B., and Olu, S. (2016). *A Review OF Soil Erodibility Case Study of Ugboju Settlement of Oturkpo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria*. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*. (2): 2455-3662.
- Bakoji, Y. M. (2017). *Soil Erosion: Farmers' Perception and Conservation Measures in the Northern Part of Taraba State, Nigeria*
- Balasubramanian, A. (2017). *Soil Erosion-Causes and Effects*. Centre for Advanced Studies in Earth Science. University of Mysore, Mysore.
- Bewket, W. (2007). Soil and water conservation intervention with conventional technologies in northwestern highlands of Ethiopia: Acceptance and adoption by farmers. *Land Use Policy*, 24 (2): 404-416.
- Ezra, P. (2014), *Effects of Gully Erosion on Farm Land*. A Case Study of Yorro LGA of Taraba State. Unpublished.
- FAO, (2015). *Status of the World's Soil Resources Report and ITPS*
- Giovannini, G., Vallejo, R. y Bautista, S. (2001). *Effects of land use and eventual fire on soil erodibility in dry Mediterranean conditions*. Forest ecology and management.
- Goldman, S., Jackson, K., and Taras, B.P.E. (1986). *Erosion and Sediment Control Handbook*. McGraw-Hill Publishing Company.
- Jankauskas, B., and Fullen, M.A. (2007). *The Relationship between Soil Organic matter content and Soil Erosion severity in Albeluvisols of the Zemaiciai upland*
- Kiflu, A., and Beyeme S. (2013). Effects of Different land use systems on selected soil properties in South Ethiopia. *Journal of Science and Environmental Management*.
- Lawrence, T.N., Justin, N.O., Valentine, M., Jacques R.T., Lews, D.L., and Jetro, N.N. (2019). Impact of Different Land Use Systems on Soil Physicochemical Properties and Microfauna Abundance in Humid Tropics of Cameroon. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*.
- Meseret, M., Addis, K. and Eyayu, M. (2015). *Assessing the Physicochemical Properties of Soil under Different Land Use Types*. *J Environ Anal Toxicol* (5): 309
- Liu, M., Han, G., Li, X., Zhang, S., Zhou, W., and Zhang, Q. (2020). *Effects of soil properties on k-factor in the Granite and limestone regions of China*. *International journal of Environmental research and public health*. (17): 801.
- Olubanjo, O. O. (2016). *Evaluation of the Effect of Soil Physico-Chemical Properties on Erodibility and Infiltration*. *Journal of Sustainable Technology*. L (8): 1 2251-0680.
- Oruonye, E. D. (2013), *The Challenges of Rural Tourism Development in Nigeria: A Case of Yorro LGA, Taraba State, Nigeria*.

- Salzmann, U., Hoelzmann, P., & Morczinek, I. (2002). Late Quaternary climate and vegetation of the Sudanian zone of northeast Nigeria. *Quaternary Research*, 58(1), 73-83.
- Taleshian, J. F., Ghajar, S. M., and Emadi, S. M. (2018). *Impact of land use change on soil erodibility*. *Global J. Environ. Sci. Manage.* 4 (1): 59-70.
- Taraba Agricultural Development Programme, TADP. (2014). *Taraba Agricultural Development Programme, Village Listing Book*.
- Ufot, N.C., and Iren, O. (2016). Effects of land use on soil physical and chemical properties in Akokwa area of Imo State, Nigeria. *Int. Journal of Life Sci Scienti.* 2 (3): 273-278
- Wischmeier, W. H., and Smith, D. D. (1978). *Predicting rainfall erosion losses: A guide to conservation planning*. USDA Handbook, 537, U.S. Dep. Agric., Washington, D.C.
- Yusuf, H. A., Oguntunde, P. G., and Lawal, A. K. (2018). *Land use effects on soil erodibility and hydraulic conductivity in Akure, Nigeria*. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*. 13 (7): 329-337.
- Zhao, W., Wei, H., Jia, L., and Daryanto, S. (2018). *Soil erodibility and its influencing factors on the Loess plateau of China*. A case study in the Ansai watershed.
- Ziegler, A. D., Tran, L. T., Giambelluca, T. W., Sidle, R. C., Sutherland, R. A., Nullet, M. A., & Vien, T. D. (2006). *Effective slope lengths for buffering hillslope surface runoff in fragmented landscapes in northern Vietnam*. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 224 (12): 104-118.